

B2-InF at the ESHRE

B2-InF has been invited to present its preliminary results at the 38th ESHRE annual meeting in Milan on 5th July 2022. This is a renowned and prestigious event in the field of Assisted Reproduction Technologies that sees hundreds of experts meet to share helpful information about ongoing research, issues and successes in the industry. Many consortium partners of the project were present as critical experts. Among them [Virginie Rozée](#), researcher at [Ined](#) and [Willem Ombelet](#), founder of the [Walking Egg](#).

We have asked [María López Toribio](#), Researcher at [Aplica Coop](#) and representative of the B2-InF project at the ESHRE annual meeting 2022, to describe her experience at the event and how the audience reacted to our presentation. Below is her answer!

"I am very grateful for the opportunity to have participated in the ESHRE congress. The ESHRE 38th Annual Meeting was a fantastic event with many exciting talks and cutting-edge ART research worldwide. In addition, the Congress took place in Milan, Italy, a really nice and beautiful city, which I had the opportunity to visit for the first time. The venue of the Congress, MiCo Milano, was wonderful with many facilities and amenities.

I presented the preliminary results of the B2-INF project in session 64 "Reproductive medicine: doctors and patients in the digital era". All the oral communications in this session were fascinating. In our project, we compared young people's perceptions of ART with the information provided by ART clinics on their websites. We found gaps between citizens' expectations and needs and the online information provided by ART clinics. The audience had interesting questions concerning the project, in particular, one health professional was interested in what the recommendations will be for policymakers.

I think all professionals are looking forward to the final outcome of the project, which will be international and national guidelines with recommendations to align young people's needs and the information provided by clinics."